

IDS in Open BIM Workflow: Potential Limitations

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the Information Delivery Specification (IDS) and its integration within the Open Building Information Modeling (BIM) workflow, examining both its potential and limitations. The research begins with an in-depth analysis of non-graphical information requirements, exploring methodologies for specifying alphanumeric data needs in BIM processes. The second chapter delves into the IDS, detailing its role, operational mechanics, and integration within the Open BIM framework, including its facets and complex constraints. The study then focuses on the practical application of IDS in Autodesk Revit, examining how IDS requirements are created and translated into IFC exports. The final chapter applies these insights to develop a proof of concept through a desktop application designed to address specific challenges in the Open BIM workflow. This comprehensive evaluation critically assesses IDS's effectiveness in improving data consistency and interoperability across BIM platforms. It offers practical solutions for enhancing the standard's application in real-world scenarios. The thesis underscores the significance of reliable data exchange and the potential legal implications of data inaccuracies in the digital construction environment.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/m8ZMPEQIrBI>

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